

COMPARISON OF FAILURE PREDICTION METHODS FOR GLASS/EPOXY AND CARBON/EPOXY LAMINATES UNDER BIAXIAL STRESS

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SUMMARY: A world wide exercise is currently underway to determine the current status of methods for predicting the strength of fibre composite laminates. The exercise is believed to be unique in that it employs an identical set of test cases, input data and output parameters for each theory evaluated, thus facilitating a direct comparison. Additionally, and most importantly, the predictions are being made by the originators of the theories. As part of the exercise, the originators were asked to predict the failure stresses and complete biaxial failure envelopes for two specific laminate configurations, namely ($\pm 30/90$) glass/epoxy and ($0/\pm 45/90$) carbon/epoxy materials. This paper contains a comparison of the predicted failure envelopes along with the input data provided to the contributors. The biaxial failure envelopes are superimposed on top of each other and grouped in a convenient manner. Bar charts are also provided, at selected stress ratios, to simplify the comparison of strength predictions for each theory.

KEYWORDS: biaxial envelopes, failure theories, international exercise, glass, carbon/epoxy, comparative study

INTRODUCTION

The origin of the world wide 'failure exercise' can be traced to an 'experts meeting' held at St Albans, England in 1991 on the subject of 'Failure of Polymeric Composites and Structures: Mechanisms and Criteria for the Prediction of Performance'. The meeting was organised by the UK Institution of Mechanical Engineers together with the UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council, who invited expert delegates from many countries to attend. The meeting took the form of a series of formal presentations interspersed with informal discussion groups. One of the principal findings which emerged was the lack of faith in the failure criteria, in current use. Attendees concluded that there was a lack of evidence to show whether any of the criteria could provide accurate and meaningful predictions of failure in composite components.

As a result of that meeting, an exercise was launched by Hinton and Soden in 1992 [1] to determine the quality of the current methods for predicting failure in composite laminates. In the exercise, selected workers in the field, including leading academics and developers of software/numerical codes, were invited to submit papers to a strictly controlled format. A series of laminate configurations, load cases and input data were defined by the organisers. Test cases were selected to challenge the theories to the full, embodying a wide range of parameters. These included fibre type (carbon and glass), matrix type (different epoxies) and the type of lay-up (unidirectional lamina and angle ply laminates, cross ply laminate, quasi-isotropic laminate and a

generally oriented laminate) and loading conditions which included uniaxial and biaxial tension, compression and shear and various combinations.

The exercise is being run in two phases:

Part A consists of papers submitted by the contributors who were asked to predict the stress/strain/strength response for each test case, having first provided a description of the theory employed and commented on any strengths or weaknesses of the method. This is a 'blind' test, as the authors have had no sight of any experimental data prior to making the predictions. At the end of this phase, predictions from the authors can be compared and contrasted against each other to identify where (or if) there is convergence or divergence.

Part B will be initiated by providing the contributors with the experimental data for each test case defined in Part A. Authors will then be in a position to compare their predictions with experimental evidence. They are then invited to provide a second paper, containing improvements to their theories or other appropriate clarifications as to the applicability of the theory or admissibility of the experimental evidence.

At the time of writing, Part A is nearing completion and Part B is about to start. In due course, Parts A and B will be published, in full, in the journal 'Composites Science and Technology'. This paper contains an overview of Part A and a slice of the results.

BACKGROUND TO THE SELECTION OF THE PARTICIPANTS

Any attempt to represent the views of all of the groups working on failure theories, worldwide, would be an impossible task. Instead, theories containing distinctly differing analytical approaches were sought, to represent as wide a spectrum as possible. Following a comprehensive publicity campaign in international journals, 38 leading exponents of certain theories were approached to participate in the exercise. For a variety of reasons, (lack of time being a common one !) a number declined to take part. In the final outcome 11 groups agreed to take part, giving the breadth and gravity required to ensure that a genuinely authentic exercise would result. A summary of the participating groups is provided in Table 1. Selected works published by these contributors and/or their groups are listed in Refs [2-13].

INPUT DATA SUPPLIED TO THE PARTICIPANTS

For all the predictions, the authors were asked to use identical input data, so that the theories could be compared on a 'level playing field'. This would also allow independent bodies to be able to attribute any differences between the outcomes of all predictions to inherent features in the formulation of the contributors' theories. Therefore, all the contributors were supplied with identical sets of properties (elastic constants, strengths, stress strain curves etc) for the laminates analyzed. Data was provided at the constituent fibre / matrix level and at the lamina level (Tables 2 to 4).

Table 1: A summary of participants and approaches represented in the exercise.

Contributor	Organisation	Approach Represented
Chamis C C, Gotsis P K and Minnetyan L	NASA Lewis, Cleveland, USA	ICAN and CODSTRAN micromechanics based software.
Hart-Smith L J	McDonnell Douglas, Longbeach, USA	Generalised Tresca.
Hart-Smith L J	McDonnell Douglas, Longbeach, USA	Max Strain theory.
Eckold G C	AEA Technology, UK	Applying British Standard pressure vessel design codes.
Edge E C	British Aerospace, Warton, UK	British Aerospace (BAe) In-house design method.
McCartney L	National Physical Laboratory, London, UK	Physically based 'Damage Mechanics'.
Puck A and Schurmann H	Technische Hochschule, Darmstadt, Germany	Physically based 3-D phenomenological models.
Wolfe W E and Butalia T S	Department of Civil Engineering, Ohio State University, Columbus, Ohio.	Maximum strain energy method, due to Sandhu (Wright Patterson Labs, Dayton, Ohio)
Sun C T and Tao J X	Purdue University School of Aeronautics & Astronautics, West Lafayette, Indiana, USA.	Linear and non-linear analysis (non-linear is FE based plus a plasticity model).
Zinoviev P, Grigoriev S V, Labedeva O V and Tairova L R	Institute of Composite Technologies, Orevo, Moskovkaya, Russia.	General application and methods.
Tsai S W and Liu K-S	Aeronautics and Astronautics Department, Stanford University, California, USA.	Interactive progressive quadratic failure criterion .
Rotem A	Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Technion-Israel Institute of Technology, Haifa, Israel.	Interactive stress theory.

Table 2: Type of unidirectional laminae, fibres and matrices used in the analysis.

Matl Type	Fibre Type	Matrix Type (all Epoxies)
1	E-Glass fibres, 1200tex, Silenka	MY750/ HY917/ DY063, Ciba Geigy
2	E-Glass fibres, 21xK43, Gevetex	LY556/HT907/DY063, Ciba Geigy
3	T300 carbon fibres, Toray	BSL914C, Ciba Geigy
4	AS4 carbon fibres, Hercules	3501-6, Hercules

Table 3: Mechanical properties of various unidirectional laminae.

Material	4	3	2	1
V_f %	60	60	62	60
E_1 GPa	126*	138	53.48	45.6
E_2 GPa	11	11	17.7	16.2
G_{12} GPa	6.6*	5.5*	5.83*	5.83*
ν_{12}	0.28	0.28	0.278	0.278
ν_{23}	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4
X_T MPa	1950**	1500	1140	1280
X_C MPa	1480	900	570	800
Y_T MPa	48	27	35	40
Y_C MPa	200**	200	114	145**
S_{12} MPa	79**	80**	72**	73**
ϵ_{1T} %	1.38	1.087	2.132	2.807
ϵ_{1C} %	1.175	0.652	1.065	1.754
ϵ_{2T} %	0.436	0.245	0.197	0.246
ϵ_{2C} %	2.0	1.818	0.644	1.2
γ_{12u} %	2	4	3.8	4
G_{TC} J/m ²	220	220	165	165
α_1 10 ⁻⁶ /°C	-1	-1	8.6	8.6
α_2 10 ⁻⁶ /°C	26	26	26.4	26.4
Curing temperature °C	177	120	120	120

* Initial modulus, ** Nonlinear stress strain curves are provided.

Table 4: Mechanical properties of fibres.

Fibre type	4	3	2	1
E_{f1} GPa	225	230	80	74
E_{f2} GPa	15	15	80	74
G_{f12} GPa	15	15	33.33	30.8
ν_{f12}	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
G_{f23}	7	7	33.33	30.8
X_{fT} MPa	3350	2500	2150	2150
X_{fC} MPa	2500	2000	1450	1450
ϵ_{f1T} %	1.488	1.086	2.687	2.905
ϵ_{f1C} %	1.111	0.869	1.813	1.959
α_{f1} 10 ⁻⁶ /°C	-0.5	-0.7	4.9	4.9
α_{f2} 10 ⁻⁶ /°C	15	12	4.9	4.9

The composite systems used in the test cases are listed in Table 5. It should be noted that the E-glass fibres were treated as being isotropic whereas the carbon fibres were treated as being anisotropic.

Table 5: Mechanical properties of various matrices.

Matrix type	4	3	2	1
E_m GPa	4.2	4.0	3.35	3.35
G_m GPa	1.567	1.481	1.24	1.24
ν_m	0.34	0.35	0.35	0.35
Y_{mT} MPa	69	75	80	80
Y_{mC} MPa	250	150	120	120
S_m MPa	50	70	-	-
ϵ_{mT} %	1.7	4	5	5
α_m $10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$	45	55	58	58

In order to exercise the theories thoroughly, several laminate configurations and load combinations were chosen. These are referred to as the ‘test cases’ and are outlined in Table 6.

Table 6: Details of the laminates and loading conditions used by the participants.

Laminate Configuration	Material Type	Loading (a wide range of biaxial stress ratios unless other wise indicated)
(0) unidirectional lamina	2 (GRP)	σ_y - τ_{xy} failure envelope
(0) unidirectional lamina	3 (CFRP)	σ_x - τ_{xy} failure envelope
(0) unidirectional lamina	3 (CFRP)	σ_x - σ_y failure envelope
(0/90) _s cross ply laminate	1 (GRP)	Uniaxial tension, SR=1/0
(±45) _s angle ply laminate	1 (GRP)	SR=1/1 and 1/-1
(±55) _s angle ply laminate	1 (GRP)	σ_x - σ_y failure envelope and SR=1/0 and 2/1
(90/±30) _s laminate	2 (GRP)	σ_x - σ_y failure envelope
(90/±30) _s laminate	2 (GRP)	σ_x - τ_{xy} failure envelope
(0/±45/90) _s quasi-isotropic laminate	4 (CFRP)	σ_x - σ_y failure envelope and SR=1/0 and 2/1

THEORETICAL RESULTS

Having described the overall scope of the failure exercise in the preceding paragraphs, a slice of the data, emerging from Part A, is presented below. In order to avoid prejudicing the ethos of the overall exercise, for the purposes of this ‘advanced’ paper the data is presented without specific reference to the originating author (readers will need to wait until Part A is published, in full, for this information). Though this reduces the impact somewhat, a number of very useful lessons can be drawn from the information. The theories used by their originators are referred to as A, B, C, D, E,.... and M. (It is worth mentioning that two contributors have used more than one theory in

their analysis). Predictions of the final failure envelopes from two of the laminate configurations, $(90/\pm 30)_s$ GRP and $(0/\pm 45/90)_s$ CFRP laminates, have been selected and are discussed more fully below. Also, a comparison has been made with the aid of bar charts between the predictions of all the theories at key stress ratios $SR = \sigma_y/\sigma_x = 1/1, -1/-1$ and $1/0$, selected from the failure envelopes.

Fig. 1: Comparison between final failure envelopes for the $(0/\pm 45/90)_s$ carbon/epoxy laminate predicted by theories E, I, L and M.

Fig. 2: Comparison between final failure envelopes for the $(0/\pm 45/90)_s$ carbon/epoxy laminate predicted by theories A, D, F, H, J and K.

AS4/3501-6, (0/±45/90)_s Quasi-Isotropic Carbon/Epoxy

Figs 1 to 2 show the final failure envelopes predicted by different contributors for this configuration. The envelopes are superimposed in order to observe the general differences between the various predictions. Figs 3-5 concentrate on comparing the predicted strengths at specified stress ratios. For this purpose, bar-charts are presented showing ‘initial’ and ‘final’ strengths (where appropriate) at biaxial stress ratios of $SR=\sigma_y/\sigma_x=1/1$, $-1/-1$ and $1/0$, selected from the failure envelopes.

Fig. 3: Initial and final failure stresses predicted by various theories (A-M) for (0/±45/90)_s laminate at SR=1/0.

Fig. 4: Initial and final failure stresses predicted by various theories (A-M) for (0/±45/90)_s laminate at SR=1/1.

Fig. 5: Initial and final failure stresses predicted by various theories for (0/±45/90)_s laminate at SR=-1/-1.

The most immediate impression one gets from Figs 1 and 2 is that the predictions fall broadly into two camps. In the first, one can see that theories (D, E, F, H, J and K) predict failure envelopes which are nearly identical in shape and in magnitude. However, in the second, each theory predicts an envelope which is unique in shape and in magnitude (A, I, L, M). Indeed there are no common features at all. A more detailed insight can be gained through examination of Figs 3-5. At the extremes of prediction (ie lowest prediction compared with highest prediction), the differences between the theories are more than 400% at a stress ratio of 1/1 (Fig 4, between I and E), more than 300% at 1/0 (Fig 3, between A and K) and more than 50% at -1/-1 (Fig 5, between L and M) for the final failure stresses. For the initial failure, the differences between the theories are more than 30 fold at SR=1/1 (Fig 4, between E and D), 20 fold at SR=1/0 (Fig 3, between E and D) and just over 70% at SR=-1/-1 (Fig 5, between L and M).

It is noted that all the theories predicted the initial failure load to be the same as the final failure under SR=-1/-1.

E-glass/LY556, (90 / ±30)_s glass/epoxy

Fig. 6: Biaxial final failure envelopes for (90/±30) laminate predicted by theories A, C, D, E, K and M.

Fig. 7: Biaxial final failure envelopes for (90/±30) laminate predicted by theories B, F, H, I, J and L.

Figs 6 to 7 show the final failure envelopes predicted by different contributors for this configuration. As above, the envelopes are superimposed in order to observe the general differences between the various predictions. Figs 8-10 concentrate on comparing the predicted strengths at specified stress ratios. For this purpose, bar-charts are presented showing ‘initial’ and ‘final’ strengths (where appropriate) at biaxial ratios of SR=1/1, -1/-1 and 1/0.

The final failure envelopes of theories C, D, E and K (Fig 6) and F, H and J (Fig 7) are similar in shape in most parts of the stress space while theories A and M (Fig 6) and B, I and L (Fig 7) do not have many common features.

Fig. 8: Predicted initial and failure stresses versus theory label for (90/±30) Glass/epoxy laminate under SR=1/0.

Fig. 9: Predicted initial and failure stresses versus theory label for (90/±30) Glass/epoxy laminate under SR=1/1.

Fig. 10: Predicted initial and failure stresses versus theory label for (90/±30) glass/epoxy laminate under SR=-1/-1.

Comparisons between the final failure stresses show that at the extremes of prediction (i.e. the lowest prediction compared with the highest prediction), the differences between the theories are 10 fold at $SR=1/0$ (Fig 8, between A and D), more than 8 fold at $SR=1/1$ (Fig 9, between A and E) and just above 50% at $SR=-1/-1$ (Fig 10, between H and L). Larger differences were noticed in the prediction of the initial failure strengths where the differences reached 33 fold for $SR=1/1$ (Fig 9, between E and B), 12 fold at $SR=1/0$ (Fig 8, between F and B) and about 4 fold at $SR=-1/-1$ (Fig 10, between E and C).

CONCLUSIONS

1. Leading failure theories, currently available, have been identified as part of a world wide exercise to determine the current status of methods for predicting the strength of fibre composite laminates.
2. The comparison between various theories is highlighting, on one hand, the richness of the theoretical understanding of the mechanics of composite materials and, on the other hand, the large diversity in the predictive accuracy of the existing theories.
3. In this paper, the leading theories have been employed, by their originators, to predict the response of two laminate configurations ($(90 / \pm 30)_s$ glass/epoxy, and $(0 / \pm 45 / 90)$ quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy laminates) when subjected to in-plane biaxial loading. The results show dramatic differences in predicted strengths, depending on the theory used. Differences (lowest to highest) in the final strengths as great as 400% have been demonstrated, even for what is often assumed to be a well understood situation, a quasi-isotropic laminate.
4. The widely diverging predictions are a clear indication that this theoretical area is far from mature and is in need of a concerted action to set it on a firmer footing. The alternative for designers will be to continue to rely on a 'make and test' philosophy, which is rapidly beginning to price composite materials / structures out of certain markets.
5. This paper contains a slice of that data from a world wide failure exercise. It is hoped that, once completed, the exercise will help contribute to an improved understanding within the composites community.

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